

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHER TRAINING ADEQUACY AND STAKEHOLDERS' DISPOSITIONS TOWARDS COMPETENCE BASED CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION IN PUBLIC JUNIOR SCHOOLS IN GARISSA COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract: *The implementation of Kenya's Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) marks a significant educational reform aimed at equipping learners with practical competencies for the 21st century. However, its success hinges heavily on the dispositions of key stakeholders teachers, school administrators, and Boards of Management whose perceptions, attitudes, and satisfaction levels significantly influence policy uptake and sustainability. Therefore, the current study was set to assess the relationship between teacher training adequacy and stakeholders' dispositions toward CBC implementation in public Junior Schools in Garissa County, Kenya. Adopting a correlational research design, the study targeted a population of 5,730 stakeholders comprising 2,865 teachers, 2,674 Board of Management (BoM) members, and 191 head teachers. Using stratified random sampling, a proportional sample of 373 respondents was selected: 187 teachers, 174 BoM members, and 12 head teachers. Data was collected through structured questionnaires for teachers and BoM members, and semi-structured interviews for head teachers. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 29. The chi-square test of independence indicated a statistically significant association between teacher training adequacy and stakeholders' dispositions towards CBC implementation in public Junior schools in Garissa, $\chi^2(150, N = 333) = 2460.13, p < .001$. The study thus recommends continuous professional development as essential for effective CBC implementation in public Junior Secondary Schools.*

Keywords: *Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) Implementation, Boards of Management, teacher training adequacy, stakeholders' dispositions, Public Junior Secondary Schools*

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INTRODUCTION

Stakeholders' dispositions defined as the beliefs, attitudes, levels of engagement, and perceptions held by teachers, parents, school leaders, and policymakers play a central role in shaping the success of education reforms. In the context of curriculum change, particularly the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC), these dispositions determine how reforms are received, interpreted, and enacted at the ground level. Dodge et al. (2024) explain that successful implementation of CBC is directly influenced by the extent to which stakeholders adopt and support new pedagogical approaches. Stakeholders' positive dispositions foster a reform-conducive environment, while negative or indifferent attitudes create resistance that hampers policy delivery and sustainability. Mpofu and Sefotho (2024) believe that local attitudes and engagement levels should be taken into account by the policymakers to be able to design curriculum frameworks, which would be effective and the stakeholder own.

The importance of stakeholder dispositions in relation to Competence Based Curriculum (CBC) implementation can hardly be overstated. The CBC thrives when teachers are adequately trained and empowered, parents are enlightened and engaged, and school administrators are supportive and competent in their leadership roles. However, when such stakeholders feel unprepared or excluded from the reform process, they tend to exhibit skepticism, low participation, and dissatisfaction, leading to poor implementation of new educational practices. Nyoni (2023) observes that while policy and resources are necessary for successful CBC implementation, the most critical factor is the willingness and preparedness of local actors to align with the curriculum's goals. Such alignment entails not only an understanding of learner centered methodologies and access to appropriate instructional support but also a positive attitude toward change within the school and community setting.

Adequate teacher training equips educators with the pedagogical competencies, curriculum mastery, and learner centered instructional strategies necessary for effective CBC delivery. The level of teacher training significantly shapes stakeholders' dispositions toward CBC implementation in public junior schools (Wamuyu, 2020). A study by Joseph, Thinguri, and Muigai (2025) revealed that teachers who are well trained and confident in CBC methodologies tend to display positive attitudes, greater commitment to curriculum reforms, and a readiness to adopt innovative teaching approaches. Similarly, school administrators, parents, and education officers are more likely to support and trust the CBC system when they perceive that teachers possess the requisite skills and competencies.

In marginalized counties such as Garissa, contextual realities including poverty, insecurity, inadequate infrastructure, and diverse cultural practices have a profound influence on CBC implementation. Owing to the limited number of trained teachers in Garissa County, poor road networks, and inadequate classroom spaces, curriculum delivery faces significant challenges (Mohamud et al., 2021). Furthermore, socio cultural factors such as nomadic lifestyles and low parental literacy rates contribute to resistance to educational transformation (Abdi, 2023). These

localized challenges collectively shape stakeholder attitudes, often resulting in reluctance, misunderstanding, or passive resistance toward CBC implementation.

Although national policies support CBC reforms, existing literature tends to overlook the qualitative dimensions of stakeholder responses in resource constrained and culturally distinct regions such as Garissa. The implications of institutional weaknesses, security challenges, and historical marginalization are rarely given adequate scholarly attention. While most studies focus on curriculum design and policy formulation, few have empirically examined the lived experiences, responses, and needs of stakeholders in such fragile contexts (Mohamud et al., 2021). This gap underscores the necessity for localized analyses that link systemic factors to stakeholder dispositions within marginalized educational environments.

Given this background, this study sought to examine the relationship between teacher training adequacy and stakeholders' dispositions toward Competence Based Curriculum implementation in public junior schools in Garissa County, Kenya, with a view to understanding how training influences stakeholder engagement and overall curriculum success.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A correlational research design was adopted for this study. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018) this research approach helps scientists detect relations without variable adjustments thus providing study results that correspond to actual observables. Educational research vitally depends on descriptive studies when observing how multiple factors affect stakeholders' reactions to educational reforms through their infrastructure and staffing conditions and teacher development methods. The design supported the main goal of evaluating CBC implementation practices alongside stakeholders' perception changes and satisfaction ratings and existing obstacles in Public junior schools.

Target Population

A total of 5730 individuals comprising of 2,865 teachers, 191 head teachers and 2674 Board of Management members drawn from the public junior schools in Garissa County were the target population. The categorization reflects the key stakeholders directly involved in the implementation and oversight of the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC), making them essential sources of information for assessing stakeholders' dispositions and institutional readiness.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

The study used simple random sampling to give sufficient representation of the teachers, the head teachers and the members of the Board of management (BoM).

The stratified random sampling was utilized since it was applicable in populations that contained various sub-groups which made it possible to create separate strata associated with distinctive features (Saunders et al. 2016). The teachers, head teachers and the BoM members served as a distinct stratum so that the stakeholders were properly represented. At each of the strata, simple random sampling was employed as a method of selecting the respondents and this assisted in eliminating bias during data collection. Thereafter, a proportional allocation was determined to select the final sample of the three categories of the stakeholders that is teachers, BoM members and the head teachers. This produced an in-depth data on stakeholders' dispositions towards Competency-Based Curriculum in Garissa County.

Sample Size

To determine the sample size for this study, the Yamane (1967) formula was applied. This formula provides a simplified approach for calculating a representative sample size from a known population. The formula is expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- N = target population
- e = margin of error (level of precision)

For this study, the target population (NNN) was 5,730 and the margin of error (eee) was 0.05, representing a 95% confidence level commonly accepted in social science research.

Substituting these values into the formula:

$$n = \frac{5730}{1 + 5730(0.05)^2} = 373$$

Sample Size Distribution: The sample was distributed proportionally among teachers, head teachers, and members of the Boards of Management (BoM) using proportional allocation. This method ensures that each subgroup is represented according to its proportion in the total population. The proportional allocation formula is given as:

$$n_i = \frac{N_i}{N} \times n$$

Where:

- n_i = sample size for each category
- N_i = population of each category
- N = total target population (5,730)
- n = total sample size (373)

Table 1 shows a summary of the application of the formula to each category of target population:

Table 1
Sample Size Distribution

Category	Target Population (N_i)	Formula	Sample Size (n_i)
Teachers	2,865	$(2,865 / 5,730) \times 373$	187
Head Teachers	191	$(191 / 5,730) \times 373$	12
BoM Members	2,674	$(2,674 / 5,730) \times 373$	174

Information on Table 1 outlined the sample size distribution drawn from a target population of 5,730 respondents, with a total sample of 373 participants selected proportionately across key stakeholder groups. The sample included 187 teachers 12 head teachers, and 174 Board of Management members. This proportional sampling ensured adequate representation of each category based on their population size, enhancing the reliability and generalizability of the study findings.

Research Instrument

This study integrated quantitative and qualitative research methods to offer an exhaustive assessment of CBC implementation processes. The principal tools for gathering data were a structured questionnaire with an interview schedule. The questionnaires gathered quantitative information by collecting teachers' questionnaire responses alongside those of members of the Board of Management (BoM), covering their perceptions and attitudes as well as their satisfaction ratings and the challenges the study encounter in implementing CBC. Eligible head teachers participated in an interview schedule to furnish an in-depth qualitative insight into their personal experience of CBC. Through the incorporation of these two research instruments, the study yielded a comprehensive grasp, mingling statistical patterns with nuanced contextual insights.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 29 and presented on mean and standard deviation. Chi-square analysis was used to analyze the inferential statistics.

For qualitative data derived from semi-structured interviews with head teachers, thematic analysis was conducted. This process involved transcribing audio-recorded interviews into textual data, followed by coding and categorizing emerging themes related to CBC implementation experiences and stakeholder attitudes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The integration of qualitative insights with quantitative findings was achieved through triangulation, thereby enriching the interpretation of results and offering a holistic understanding of stakeholder dispositions toward CBC in a complex, marginalized educational setting.

RESULTS

Teacher Training Adequacy and Stakeholders' Dispositions towards CBC Implementation in Public Junior Schools

To assess the adequacy of teacher training and its influence on stakeholders' dispositions toward Competence Based Curriculum implementation, the study sought participants' views on various aspects of teacher training and professional development. Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with statements related to teachers' qualifications, exposure to CBC-specific training, participation in professional development activities, and access to post-training support. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Response on Teacher Training and Stakeholder's Dispositions (N=368)

Items	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
Teachers in this school have the professional qualifications required for CBC teaching.	1.9	11.7	16.0	47.6	22.8
Teachers have received CBC-specific training that aligns with the curriculum requirements.	1.1	8.4	24.5	51.1	14.9
Teachers regularly attend CBC-related professional development workshops or in-service training.	0.0	13.6	25.3	50.5	10.6
The training provided adequately equipped teachers with the skills to implement CBC effectively.	2.2	8.4	28.5	44.6	16.3
Teachers are offered post-training support such as mentoring or coaching on CBC practices.	0.8	16.3	19.6	47.0	16.3

Key: Strongly Disagree (SD); Disagree (D), Neutral (N); Agree (A); Strongly Agree (SA).

As shown in Table 2, the majority of respondents generally agreed that teachers possess the professional qualifications required for CBC teaching, with 47.6% agreeing and 22.8% strongly agreeing, while only 1.9% strongly disagreed and 11.7% disagreed.

Similarly, slightly more than half of the respondents (51.1%) agreed and 14.9% strongly agreed that teachers had received CBC-specific training aligned with curriculum requirements, indicating positive perceptions of curriculum-based preparation. However, a notable 24.5% of respondents remained neutral, suggesting that while training opportunities exist, they may not be uniformly accessible or comprehensive.

Regarding professional development, 50.5% of respondents agreed and 10.6% strongly agreed that teachers regularly attend CBC-related workshops or in-service training, whereas 25.3% were neutral and 13.6% disagreed. This finding implies moderate engagement in continuous professional learning.

In terms of training adequacy, 44.6% of respondents agreed and 16.3% strongly agreed that the training provided adequately equipped teachers with the necessary skills to implement CBC effectively, while 28.5% remained neutral. This suggests a generally favorable perception of teacher preparedness, though a substantial portion of respondents expressed uncertainty.

Concerning post-training support, 47.0% agreed and 16.3% strongly agreed that teachers received ongoing assistance such as mentoring or coaching on CBC practices. Nevertheless, 19.6% of respondents were neutral and 17.1% either disagreed or strongly disagreed, reflecting gaps in sustained follow-up support after training.

Overall, the findings indicate that while most teachers in public junior schools in Garissa County are qualified and have received some form of CBC-oriented training, inconsistencies remain in the depth and continuity of professional development and support mechanisms. These variations may influence stakeholders' confidence and overall disposition toward the successful implementation of the Competence Based Curriculum.

Qualitative data was also sought regarding the training programs provided to teachers for CBC implementation. In response, Head Teacher 1 observed that:

In our school, teachers have participated in several training programs aimed at equipping them with the skills and knowledge required for effective CBC implementation. These include Teacher Professional Development (TPD) workshops organized by the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) and the Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD), focusing on CBC pedagogy, learner-centered approaches, and formative assessment techniques. (Personal Communication, Head Teacher 1, July 30, 2025)

With reference to the effectiveness of these training programs in preparing teachers for CBC, Head Teacher 2 (July 30, 2025) explained that:

From my perspective as a head teacher, the training programs provided for CBC implementation have been moderately effective but still leave notable gaps. On the positive side, the study has helped teachers understand the philosophy of CBC, shift towards learner-centered teaching, and apply practical, hands-on activities that develop competencies rather than focusing solely on content delivery. The workshops and seminars have also improved teachers' ability to design performance-based assessments and integrate ICT where resources are available. (Personal Communication, Head Teacher 2, July 30, 2025)

Another head teacher reported the following:

The effectiveness of teacher training programs has been reduced by several factors. First, the short duration of the training sessions, often just a few days, limits the depth of understanding and practical application. Second, participation is inconsistent, with not all teachers trained at the same time, creating disparities in knowledge and classroom practice. Third, there is limited follow-up and mentorship, meaning teachers often struggle to apply what they learned once back in their classrooms. Lastly, the evolving nature of the CBC means teachers must continuously adapt to changes, yet training updates are not always provided in a timely manner. (Personal Communication, Head Teacher 3, July 30, 2025)

The qualitative findings complement the quantitative results by illustrating not only the extent of teachers' participation in CBC-related training but also the perceived adequacy and challenges of these programs. While the descriptive data reflected high levels of teacher engagement in professional development, the narratives from head teachers highlighted gaps related to training duration, consistency, and follow-up support.

Relationship between Teacher Training Adequacy and Stakeholders' Dispositions towards CBC Implementation in Public Junior Schools

To determine whether a significant relationship existed between teacher training adequacy and stakeholders' dispositions towards the Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) implementation in public junior schools in Garissa County, Kenya, a chi-square test of independence was conducted.

Table 3

Chi-Square Test Results on Teacher Training Adequacy and Stakeholders' Dispositions towards CBC Implementation (N = 333)

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2460.134 ^a	150	.000
Likelihood Ratio	1182.970	150	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	208.596	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	333		

Note. ^a 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5.

The chi-square test of independence indicated a statistically significant association between teacher training adequacy and stakeholders' dispositions towards CBC implementation, $\chi^2(150, N = 333) = 2460.13, p < .001$. This suggests that the adequacy of teacher training is significantly related to how stakeholders perceive and support the implementation of the Competence-Based Curriculum in public junior schools in Garissa County.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that the adequacy of teacher training has a significant influence ($p < .001$) on stakeholders' dispositions toward the implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) in public junior schools in Garissa County. Most respondents agreed that teachers possessed the necessary professional qualifications and had received relevant training on CBC. The study further showed that many teachers regularly attend professional development sessions and receive some level of follow-up support through mentoring and coaching. These results point to the fact that teacher preparedness plays a crucial role in ensuring that the curriculum is implemented effectively. When teachers are well trained and confident, they are better able to apply the learner-centered methods that are central to CBC.

The positive views expressed by the respondents are consistent with the findings of Mwangi and Mwaura (2021), who established that teachers with adequate professional preparation tend to have stronger motivation and greater confidence in implementing new curricula. Similarly, Koech and Waweru (2021) observed that continuous in-service training enhances teachers' pedagogical skills and improves learning outcomes. The results also echo the work of Mutonya (2022), who found that teachers' attitudes toward CBC depend on the adequacy of professional learning opportunities and access to instructional materials. Respondents in this study expressed generally positive attitudes toward CBC, indicating that professional development programs have helped build confidence. However, some respondents remained neutral or uncertain,

suggesting that challenges related to resource availability and limited participation in curriculum planning still exist, as Mutonya also observed. The current study therefore supports the argument that the success of educational reforms depends largely on the extent to which teachers are trained, equipped, and supported to interpret and implement curriculum changes.

Even though most respondents felt that teachers were adequately trained, a few expressed concerns about the quality and consistency of training as well as the adequacy of post-training support. This view is consistent with the findings of Njenga (2022), who noted that disparities in the design and delivery of CBC training programs have created uneven levels of teacher preparedness across different regions. The findings reflect the argument by Owusu-Fordjour (2021), who observed that teacher preparation directly influences stakeholder attitudes because well-trained teachers demonstrate competence and confidence in their work, which builds trust among parents, administrators, and other education actors. Similarly, in this study, positive perceptions of teacher preparedness appeared to encourage broader stakeholder support for CBC implementation in Garissa County. The present study mirrors these findings and highlights the need for more structured professional development programs that offer ongoing coaching and follow-up to help teachers refine their instructional practices.

The inferential analysis further confirmed a strong and positive relationship between teacher training adequacy and stakeholders' attitudes toward CBC implementation. The correlation was statistically significant, indicating that teachers' competence and confidence influence how other stakeholders, such as head teachers and members of the Board of Management, perceive and support curriculum implementation efforts. These findings are in line with the conclusions of Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), who emphasized that when teachers receive proper training and support, they not only perform better in the classroom but also inspire confidence among other education stakeholders, thereby creating a more supportive environment for curriculum change. The results also echo the work of Mutonya (2022), who found that teachers' attitudes toward CBC depend on the adequacy of professional learning opportunities and access to instructional materials. Respondents in this study expressed generally positive attitudes toward CBC, indicating that professional development programs have helped build confidence. However, some respondents remained neutral or uncertain, suggesting that challenges related to resource availability and limited participation in curriculum planning still exist, as Mutonya also observed.

In general, the findings demonstrate that teacher training adequacy is a key driver of both teacher performance and stakeholder support for CBC. When teachers feel adequately prepared and supported, their sense of ownership and commitment increases, and this positive attitude tends to influence others involved in school management and policy implementation. However, where teachers feel inadequately trained or unsupported, the overall success of CBC may be compromised. It is therefore essential for education policymakers and training institutions to continue investing in high-quality and continuous teacher training programs. Strengthening mentorship and follow-up mechanisms can ensure that teachers remain well equipped to deliver

learner-centered instruction and to sustain the goals of the Competency-Based Curriculum in Kenya's education system.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that teacher training is a central factor in implementing the Competence Based Curriculum (CBC) effectively. Teachers with professional qualifications aligned to CBC, who had received specific training in relevant learning areas such as STEM, life skills, and creative arts, were better equipped to conduct learner centered lessons. Regular participation in workshops, in service training, and access to mentoring and coaching further strengthened their skills and confidence. The results emphasize that sustained capacity building and professional development are necessary for teachers to adapt to CBC methodologies and improve curriculum outcomes. Teacher training was therefore identified as a strong predictor of stakeholders' positive dispositions and effective curriculum delivery.

The study recommends continuous professional development as essential for effective CBC implementation. The Ministry of Education and teacher training institutions should design and provide CBC specific training programs, including workshops, in service sessions, mentoring, and coaching, regularly updated to reflect evolving curriculum demands. School administrators should facilitate teacher participation in these programs and provide structured post training support to ensure the application of newly acquired skills. Teachers, in turn, should actively engage in professional development opportunities and consistently apply learned competencies to enhance learner centered instruction and improve overall curriculum effectiveness.

For further study, the study recommends an investigation into the role of different stakeholders, including teachers, parents, administrators and government, in the effective implementation of Competency Based Curriculum in Public Junior Secondary Schools.

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